

Climate Intervention: Building Blocks for Science–Policy Dialogues

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Outline

Physics of Climate Change

Actions to Cope with the Problem

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Adaptation

Climate Intervention

Solar Radiation Modification (SRM)

Marine Clouds Brightening

Thinning Cirrus Clouds

Stratospheric Aerosol Injection

SRM: Benefits, Risks and Challenges

Source: IITM - Pune

Physics of Climate Change

The First Industrial Revolution 1760-1840

The great achievement:

the steam engine
=
burning of coal and wood

<https://br.pinterest.com/pin/516717757224026123/>

Human development has **changed** the **concentration of gases** in the atmosphere.

With natural greenhouse effect
Earth's mean temperature 1850-1900: 13.5°C

With human contribution
Earth's mean temperature 2024: 15.1°C
Increase of 1.6°C

Air Temperature

Increase in the global average temperature

The Earth is **1.6°C*** warmer since the pre-industrial period.

*2024 anomaly compared to the 1850-1900 period.

2023 and 2024 → global warming + El Niño

2025 projected to finish as 2nd or 3rd warmest year on record

Annual global surface air temperature increase above pre-industrial level

<https://climate.copernicus.eu/surface-air-temperature-october-2025>

PROGRAMME OF
THE EUROPEAN UNION

IMPLEMENTED BY

The global average air temperature will continue to increase.

Dvorak et al. (2022) DOI:[10.1038/s41558-022-01372-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01372-y)

Currently implemented policies on greenhouse gas emissions are projected to lead to a peak global-mean **warming this century of about 3.1°C** (United Nations, 2024).

This warming can lead →

Tipping points in the climate system

Geological and ecological systems around the globe are losing their equilibrium as a result of climate change. Some of these changes have a reinforcing effect on climate change, making it accelerate to the point that it can no longer be stopped.

After Lenton et al. (Nature 2019)

Consequences of the increase in the concentration of CO₂ and other gases in the atmosphere

Change in the chemical composition of the atmosphere

Increase in the greenhouse effect

Increase in the global average air temperature

Disturbances in the climate system

Extreme weather and climate events and changes in climate regimes etc.

Wang F, Harindintwali J.-D., Wei K., et al., (2023). Climate change: Strategies for mitigation and adaptation. *The Innovation Geoscience* **1**(1), 100015. doi: [10.59717/j.xinn-geo.2023.100015](https://doi.org/10.59717/j.xinn-geo.2023.100015)

Greenhouse Effect

Consequences of the increase in the concentration of CO₂ and other gases in the atmosphere

20:40Z
07 Nov
2025

Imagens aéreas da destruição após passagem de tornado em Rio Bonito do Iguçu, no Paraná — Foto: Reuters/via Governo do Estado do Paraná

<https://g1.globo.com/meio-ambiente/noticia/2025/11/09/ciclone-extratropical-que-atingiu-parana-comeca-a-se-afastar-para-alto-mar-neste-domingo.ghtml>

<https://www.reuters.com/world/hurricane-melissa-live-jamaica-braces-storm-2025-10-28/>

Last updated 10 days ago

Hurricane Melissa as it happened:
Storm barreled through Cuba as
Jamaica reported four deaths

Consequences of the increase in the concentration of CO₂ and other gases in the atmosphere

<https://insideclimatenews.org/tags/heat-stress/>

<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/greenhouse-gases>

<https://earth.org/causes-and-effects-of-water-shortage/>

The Paris Agreement (2015)

aims to limit global warming compared to pre-industrial levels to not more than **2 °C** by the end of the century and pursue efforts to limit the temperature increase to **1.5°C** above pre-industrial levels.

To reach the Paris Agreement → greenhouse gas emissions, to peak in 2025, **fall by more than 40% by 2030** and **achieve 'net-zero' by 2050** (when greenhouse gas emissions from human activity and their removal from the atmosphere are in balance).

Even if all emissions were stopped today, the greenhouse effect would continue because greenhouse gases have a long lifetime in the atmosphere, with some lasting for centuries.

Actions to Cope with the Problem

MITIGATION

...slowing global warming

Examples

- Reduce greenhouse gas emissions
- Improve energy efficiency
- Increase carbon sequestration
- Preserve ecosystems

ADAPTATION

...reducing vulnerability to impacts

Examples

- Prepare for heat extremes
- Protect against flooding
- Use water more efficiently
- Develop drought tolerant crops

CLIMATE INTERVENTION

...deliberate modification of the climate

Examples

- Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR)
- Solar radiation Modification (SRM)

CLIMATE INTERVENTION

UNEP, One Atmosphere, 2023:
“SRM is the only option that could cool the planet within years.”

Marine Cloud Brightening (MCB)

Idea inspired on low clouds observed from satellites along the ship tracks

More aerosols → increase the number of cloud droplets → but with smaller size → more reflected sunlight.

In addition, it increases cloud lifetime (The Royal Society, 2025).

Cirrus Cloud Thinning (CCT)

It does not affect the incoming solar radiation but rather the infrared radiation emitted by the Earth.

The idea behind CCT is to increase the formation of larger ice crystals instead of numerous smaller ones, as larger crystals would retain less infrared radiation. To achieve this, additional particles, such as sulphate, aircraft soot, or mineral dust, would need to be released into the atmosphere to serve as condensation nuclei at those altitudes (Tully et al., 2021).

<https://www.knightoptical.com/news/knight-optical-presents-the-world-of-geo-engineering/>

By increasing the size of the ice crystals, more infrared radiation can escape from the atmosphere

Stratospheric Aerosol Injection (SAI)

Idea inspired on the huge eruptions

In the years following a huge volcanic eruption, the planet's average temperature decreases. Why?

Global surface temperature (1940-2016)

Aerosols injected into the stratosphere increase the planet's albedo

Stratospheric Aerosol Injection: Fast, Cheap, Imperfect – with new Governance Challenges

SAI is the most studied.

To cool Earth 1°C with SAI:

- ~ 100 – 200 aircraft modified to fly high
10 flights per day
- Putting ~ 10 Mt Sulfur dioxide/year in stratosphere
sulfur = enxofre
- Direct cost ~ \$10-20 B USD per year

10 Mt Sulfur/year is one Pinatubo eruption, which is ~ the mass of 49,000 Statues of Liberty

Source of this huge amount?
Petroleum refining and natural gas processing remove sulfur compounds.

SRM: Benefits, Risks and Challenges

Benefits

If done prudently to reduce climate risk, SAI could ...

- Reduce temperatures
- Reduce disruption to rainfall
- Slow rate of sea level rise
- Reduce intensity of tropical/extratropical storms
- Reduce extreme heat events

SRM: Benefits, Risks and Challenges

Risks

- SRM cannot fully undo effects of elevated CO₂
- Environmental impacts:
 - Delayed ozone recovery
 - Small increases in acid deposition, air pollution
- Most research is on climate effects: More serious unknowns about:
 - Agriculture
 - Ecosystems and Biodiversity
 - Human health

Acidic water enters the plants and causes the minerals to dissolve and get carried away.

SRM: Benefits, Risks and Challenges

Challenges

There is no international law regulating SRM; any state may legally use it.

“The absence of legal prohibition does not mean permission in practice.”

- Who decides whether and how to use SRM?
- How will it be controlled, with what aims?
- Might some try to use it unjustly, seek regional advantage?
- Might it trigger conflict or destabilization?
Or spur stronger global governance?

SRM: Benefits, Risks and Challenges

Challenges

More scientific studies are needed on the benefits and risks of SRM.

It is necessary to bring together **scientists** and **decision-makers** to discuss this controversial topic.

SRM: Benefits, Risks and Challenges

From previous meetings with **decision-makers**, **DEGREES Initiative members** took note of **the most common questions**:

How would you do this?

Who would do it? Who could? How soon?

Is anyone doing this now?

Does it work? (with a lot of possibility for confusion about what “work” means ...)

Is this like cloud seeding or other weather modification?

How confident can we be that this will reduce harmful climate change for exactly my location?

What are the worst things that could fail? What harms could it cause?

What if it does work or causes harm? What can be done about that?

Who is doing this, and why – and can we trust them?

Why haven't we heard about this before? Is this some crazy new idea?

We do not have answers to many of them.

Final Message

SE FICAR O BICHO COME

SE CORRER O BICHO PEGA

SRM without right
governance

...SE UNIR O BICHO FOGE !!

Scientists
+
Government

Thank you for your attention!

References

SRM Basic

<https://royalsociety.org/-/media/policy/projects/solar-radiation-modification/solar-radiation-modification-policy-briefing.pdf>

SAI Basic

<https://news.climate.columbia.edu/2025/10/21/how-hard-is-it-to-dim-the-sun/>

SAI simulation design <https://reflective.org/simulating-the-impacts-of-sai-deployment/>

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